

Talent Management Strategies and Employee Performance in TransNzoia County, Kenya

Monica Chemutai Sutter^{1*}, Dr. Elizabeth Nambuswa Makokha (PhD)^{1,2}

¹College of Human Resource Development, Department of Entrepreneurship and Procurement Leadership and Management. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, P.O. Box 62000 - 00200, Nairobi Kenya

²College of Human Resource Development, Department of Entrepreneurship and Procurement Leadership and Management. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, P.O. Box 62000 - 00200, Nairobi Kenya

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of talent management strategies and employee performance in TransNzoia County government. The study was guided by four specific objectives that included: to examine the influence of talent attraction and employee performance in TransNzoia county, Kenya. The study was anchored on the expectancy theory. The study adopted correlational research design. The population of the study consisted of 1005 employees of TransNzoia County government. A stratified random sampling technique was adopted by the study to select a sample of one hundred and sixty three respondents to be drawn from the departmental heads and other senior officers within the sub-departments of the county. The study used structured Likert-scale questionnaires as instruments for collecting primary data. The study used descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze data. Inferential statistical analysis included multiple linear regression model that presented the relationship among variables. The findings of the study indicated that talent management strategies influenced employee performance in the county by; talent attraction ($r=0.729$, $\beta=0.564$, $t=3.156$). That the county selection and recruitment process was not free and fair but heavily based on nepotism and tribalism and that promotions were not conducted in a free and fair manner. The study recommendations included: The County to ensure that measures are put in place to create good organizational climate that attract the right talent where recruitment process is scientific. The findings of the study were significant to both the county leadership and of other counties in Kenya together with management of other different organizations in different sectors both private and public as well as adding to existing literature in the field of human resource management in general.

Keywords: Talent Attraction, Employee performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Employee performance common to most jobs includes quantity of output, timelines of output, presence at work and cooperativeness (Mathis & Jackson, 2024). Knott and Linge (2021) define employee performance as a measure of the quality of a person's job execution. Many organizations review the performance of their employees on a quarterly or annual basis to determine the areas that require improvement. Employee performance reflects on the productivity of any given organization and therefore, needs serious consideration. Elnaga and Imran (2023), define employee performance as output produced by employees based on a given job description that contribute to the realization of organizational objectives. It involves all aspects which directly or indirectly affect and relate to the work of the employees.

One of the elements that is assessable is the employee performance through the level of their productivity. Several researches have been introducing various methods to evaluate organizational performance in terms of the quality of work they produce, quantity in terms of numbers of output and how innovative and creative they are as individuals (Prajogo,

2007). This help employees accomplish the work in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to them during a specified period. In other words, the assessment systems in selecting new employees to fill a role in an organization must have some standard parameters that can be relied upon. Once the position has been filled then the organization should follow a holistic approach in talent management for purposes of improving the performance of the employees. Knott and Linge (2021) argued that the effectiveness transfer on the behavior of employees as a result of human resource management which also proves a positive association. The ideal employee is one who has excellent skills and operates in a productive environment. Organizations can only tap into the full potential of employees by providing them with the necessary tools to succeed. The importance of employee performance must therefore be understood by the management and sincere efforts must be put in that direction. The management of the company taking timely steps in that direction will be in position to develop and motivate the people to do so (Mendez & Stander, 2022). Thus it was on this basis that the study aimed to determine the influence of talent management practices on employee performance in TransNzoia county government, Kenya.

Talent consists of those individuals who can make a difference to organizational performance either through their immediate contribution or, in the longer term, by demonstrating the highest levels of potential" (CIPD, 2021). Talent management is defined as the process of identifying, development, recruitment, retaining and deployment of high potential individuals at the workplace (Knott & Linge, 2021). According to Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart and Wright (2020), talent management is the systematic and planned effort to attract, retain, develop, and motivate highly skilled employees and managers. It can also be defined as a comprehensive and strategic approach to human resource and business planning that increases organizational effectiveness (Mwangangi, 2023). The primary focus of talent management is ensuring the harmony of the organization's employees with the right job and roles, and responsibilities contributing to the institution's strategic goals (De Varo, 2020). Effective management of top talent in the government sector is integral to employee performance. The changing workplace dynamics and a shortfall of employees with scarce expertise have forced employers to understand better the various factors that affect their performances.

In the modern day competition, talent has become a precious resource, sought and fought over by competitors in a global 'war for talent' (Noe *et al.*, 2020). For most organizations, filling key positions is a very important means of developing and ensuring sustainability of the competitive edge (Obedgiu, Lagat, & Sang, 2022). Retaining talented employees is the priority of many organizations and it is the key differentiator of human capital management (Mohammed, 2019).

Organizations have increasingly recruited talent away from their competitors, creating talent management tension (Capelli, 2020). The demand for competent employees is high especially for key decision-making workforce; therefore organizations are exposed to a continuous competitive fight for the best and talented employees (Kibui, 2020). Satisfied employees due to good talent management strategies tend to be committed to an organization and employees who are satisfied and committed are more likely to perform better leading to better overall organizational performance (Ngirande & Muzana, 2020). Talent management strategies consist of a wide range of activities which different organizations adopt such as compensation management, talent attraction, talent development, talent retention, performance management, competency management, skill development, training and development, learning and development, leadership development, succession planning, career management, workforce planning and many others (Mwangangi, 2023). The strategies adopted generally differ from industry to industry in many cases and certain practices are more suitable for certain industries over others.

A study led by KPMG (2019) on professional stability found that, because of the unsure financial condition, majority of members considered employee rewards their main concern and catalyst towards serious engagement and hence performance. Despite the fact that the discoveries likewise uncovered that approximately two-thirds of employees probably going to present with an open or non-benefit organization as appeared differently in relation to a private part because of the downturn. In the USA, for example, national job protection has been highly dependent on economic and market conditions owing to the capitalist framework that facilitates and supports the growth of entrepreneurship and limited policy interference in businesses which leads to higher employee performance levels (Alias, Othman, Loon, Ridzuan & Krishnan, 2023). An assortment of factors, for example, business contracts, aggregate haggling game plans, work laws and individual factors, for example, age, work understanding, vocation useful area, work showcase, workforce, and so on., assume a huge job in evaluating an employees' performance. Another genuine, significant or proper aptitudes

and past experience expected by the businesses and subject to the current financial condition and market atmosphere may likewise ensure work insurance for people hence motivating them to perform (Jiang, Xiao, Qi & Xiao, 2019).

According to Kibui (2018), talent management in Africa has been a big concern due to low company remuneration and the presence of uncompetitive work environments, which have a negative impact on employee performance and eventual desire to stay with the organization. According to Olufemi, Afegbua, and Etim (2020), a strategic talent management strategy is needed to improve the performance of staff in Nigerian public sector organizations as it will help maintain high skills, commitment, productivity, and low employment costs which will eventually lead to high employee performance in organizations. Challenges in improving employee performance are being encountered by a lot of developing countries in Africa (Dixit & Bhati, 2021). Crook, Todd, Combs, Woehr and Ketchen (2019) observe that through talent management the individual's capacity to have knowledge, skills and attitudes to enable the firms' survival as well as to improve the individual's capability in performance has become the main strength of the competitiveness of the organizations. Therefore, talent management facilitates the improvement of the employees' performance positively towards the achievement of both the employee and organizational objectives.

Knott and Linge (2021) indicated that talent management strategies implemented in Kenya (i.e. by Suraya property group limited) should be aimed at guaranteeing employee performance and hence organizational performance. Similarly, Nchuchuwe and Etim (2020) point out that Kenyan public sector organizations cannot provide a comprehensive list of commendable work unless they have the right staff. As a result, talent management considers the benefit of putting the right people in the right jobs, recognizing the critical need for any organization to have skilled, dedicated and competent staff who can help achieve the organization as well as personal priorities and goals. The lack of attainment of required employee performance levels in the counties has had adverse effects on service delivery. Several studies have been done on talent management (Ochieng, 2019; Ndung'u & Omondi, 2019; Silvia, 2020; Omondi, 2021; Wambui, 2022), many of whom have studied about how talent management affects competitive advantage (Whysall, Owtram & Brittain, 2019), however, there is limited research that has been done on how talent management influence employee performance in TransNzoia County, Kenya. Nonetheless, despite a significant growth in talent management literature, most studies were carried out in other sectors (Karuri, 2019; Ndung'u & Omondi, 2019; Kibui, Gachunga & Namusonge, 2020). Therefore, study sought to examine the influence of talent attraction on employee performance in TransNzoia County, Kenya.

2. TALENT ATTRACTION AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

The talent management process coincides with recruiting and hiring processes (Alruwaili, 2018). There are several approaches to hire qualified candidates, but one of the main elements of recruiting and selection is job analysis (Bibi, 2018). This is viewed as a significant errand for the association to draw in a pool of ability and afterward select the expected individual from the pool that at last leads the organization to progress (Anthony & Taylor, 2020). Ability fascination through enlistment is a basic advance to help figure out which workers can serve the associations adequately while determination is explained as ability appraisal capacities to satisfy the activity task at last lead to the perfect individual being selected in the correct activity (Bratton & Gold, 2023). Recruitment is an act of discovering likely specialists for existing or arranged positions and employing is a method of picking the best individual for the work (Oaya, Ogbu, & Remilekun, 2017). Enrollment is depicted as a chase for candidates while the choice is outlined as the person to carry out the responsibility. Recruiting and choosing the correct worker in the correct activity will inevitably influence both the organization and the presentation of representatives (Dixit & Dean, 2022).

According to Pahos and Galanaki (2019), enlistment and determination might be a method for improving individual worker execution through acclimating capable people just as giving chances to hierarchical execution. They additionally indicated positive connections between staffing rehearses (enlistment and choice) and representative execution (Rahmany, 2018). Using deductive methodology to determine the impact on workplace efficiency of recruiting and selection procedures. The results indicate a productive partnership regarding recruiting, hiring and success of the company. Jolaosho, Olayink, Raji, & Akintan (2018) conducted studies on the impact of recruiting and hiring on job performance in the telecommunication industry. The study revealed that recruitment and selection had a positive impact on employee performance. They also argued that recruiting and evaluation was of greater significance for retaining qualified workers who will do well in the future in order to meet the organizational goals. According to Abbott and De Cieri (2022), work life balance is a field of increasing significance for workers and employers alike. Employees use it to manage job and non-work positions and businesses need it to productively raise and reduce costs. The factors of work-life harmony can be

traced to shifts in the population allocation of labor, technical progress and the tradition of the opening hour of contemporary society 24/7 (Mbugua & Njenga, 2020). Although there is no clear concept of work-life balance, several common trends have emerged: workers reach a reasonable work-life balance, employers' job program that will help increase the morale of employees by delivering a variety of tailored work-life activities that improves firm execution and doesn't bring about noteworthy cost increments for bosses (Abbott & De Cieri, 2022).

Work-life balance requires, on the one side, a reasonable prioritization of employment (career and ambition) and existence (health, enjoyment, recreation, family and profound turn of events). Related however more extensive definitions incorporate way of life equalization, and presence progression. In its broadest importance, work-life balance is portrayed as an agreeable level of commitment or fit between the different jobs in an individual's life. Investigating the everyday existences of different laborers, time and weariness are two significant issues that should be handled so as to keep up work life balance. Managing these two factors is the key to a good equilibrium of work life (Kossek & Ozeki, 2018).

Work-life balance does not imply devoting equivalent quantities of time to paid and unpaid positions; it is described, in its broadest context, as an agreeable level of investment or fit between the different jobs in an individual's life. In spite of the fact that implications and understandings that vary, work-life offset is generally equivalent with a trade-off between the measure of time and vitality that somebody gives to work and individual interests so as to hold a feeling of complete balance in presence (Mbugua & Njenga, 2020). Work life balance is about individuals having charge over when, where and how they work. There is a feeling that work-life balance is just with regards to what the organization accomplishes for the person (Kumar & Mohd, 2019). According to Hartel, Steel and Shultz (2020), organizations can execute different work-life adjusting activities that can assist representatives with adjusting work and family obligations better, improve prosperity and convey hierarchical advantages. There are a wide scope of family neighborly activities that include, however are not confined to: adaptable working hours, vocation sharing, low maintenance occupations, short work weeks, parental leave, and working from home, kid care benefits nearby.

According to Naktiyok and Iscan (2021), it is more popular for people to do at least some of their daily job from home rather than heading into the workplace. This form of arrangement is also referred to as telework or telecommuting and can be helpful for workers by encouraging them to: schedule their working day around their personal and family needs; Minimizing work-related costs; minimizing travel time; and operating in a less frustrating and destructive environment. It may also help accommodate employees who are unable to leave home because of particular disabilities. The idea that teleworkers may make use of this additional versatility to focus on their specific peak production times may also have a positive effect on the bottom line of an organization. Given these advantages and the public coverage that telecommuting has gained, relatively few labor arrangements include clauses related to telework. The absence of telecommuting statements is expected, to some extent, to the way that not all occupations are appropriate for such a game plan (Phillipa, Ishaq & Kola, 2023). Moreover, managers might be worried about beginning execution costs, expected legitimate commitments and troubles in supervising and evaluating telecommuters' exhibition. Worker's guilds may differ with work-at - home provisos on the off chance that they see them as prompting more prominent representative separation, decreased professional stability and advancement openings, and diminished assurance of well-being and security (Mbugua & Njenga, 2020).

In addition, part-time contracts may allow individuals with health conditions, illnesses or minimal available time (e.g. students) to participate in the activity showcase improve their gifts and procure work understanding. At last, they will make things simpler for the individuals who have taken profession breaks to reappear the working environment particularly moms (or fathers) who remained at home to bring up their youngsters or have a consistent way for retirement-inclined specialists (Bibi, 2018). From the business' perspective, the usage, where possible, of part-time employees will help optimize the use of human capital and improve organizational efficiency by offering extra coverage at peak times. Part-time jobs can therefore be found unsatisfactory for those workers who may like to raise their wages by working fewer hours, thereby giving a superior personal satisfaction for their families. The European Study of Working Conditions demonstrated that 85% of the individuals who work less than 30 hours seven days were content with their work-life balance (Naktiyok & Iscan, 2021). Part-time employment is one technique used often by employees who want to manage their career and personal life better. Part-time jobs in wealthier, higher-level professions would be encouraged in leadership roles in the business environment (Clarke et al., 2020).

According to Juhdi, Pa'wan and Hansaram (2019), job security is characterized as a guarantee of continuity of employment for an employee due to the general economic conditions in the world. It concerns the probability or likelihood of a person retaining his or her job. This deals with workers' odds of holding their jobs, such that they are not unemployed. Shoaib, Noor, Tirmizi and Bashir (2019) claim that workers that are not or cannot be secured over a fixed amount of time on an undefined contract are considered to lose work protection thereby affecting their performance. It is often regarded as the workers safe from the risk of getting fired from their current work or employment loss. A few occupations and business-related practices give preferred work environment solidness over others. Professional stability is the affirmation or certainty of a representative that they will keep up their present place of employment for a more extended time frame, as they wish.

It has been considered that some forms of employment and business workers are extremely safe at work. For example, government employment, college employment, healthcare jobs and law enforcement jobs are assumed to be quite stable whilst, on the other hand, private sector jobs are generally viewed to provide poorer job protection and can often rely on business, location, profession and other variables. Work protection often relies on whether or not people are employable, and whether or not employers use their expertise. While job laws may provide some protection against the possibility of unemployment, they just have a minimal impact to the individuals' job security. The truth remains that workers require the correct qualifications to provide effective work protection and hence their performance (Alias *et al.*, 2023).

3. METHOD

A correlational research design was considered the most appropriate research design for this study based on the research objectives. The target population for this study was all of the 1005 employees of TransNzoia County government. The study employed stratified random sampling technique to select departmental heads and other senior, and middle management personnel from the ten departments of TransNzoia County government. This enabled the proportionate participation of all the senior personnel of TransNzoia County government. The study used simple random sampling in the creation of the sample size from each stratum and for distribution of the questionnaires.

The sample size of 163 **respondents** was then determined using the following model by Nasiurma (2000); - data collection instrument was structured questionnaire. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of data collection instrument. This study used both inferential and descriptive statistics to summarize the demographic profiles of respondents and the results were presented in charts and tables. Percentages were used to analyse and present the various responses to statements that helped the study to measure the specific variables. Correlation and regression were inferentially used to test for the study variables. The multiple linear regression model was used to establish the direction of the relationship between talent management strategies and employee performance.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Analysis of effect of Employee Performance in TransNzoia County

The collected data on the employee performance in TransNzoia county government was tabulated as presented below;

Table 4.1: Employee Performance in TransNzoia County Government

Statements	SD %	D %	UD %	A %	SA %	Mean	STDEV
Talent development has increased my work output and overall organization productivity	4	9	11	26	50	3.847	1.261
Since the introduction of talent development the employees productivity has really improved in the organization	9	17	27	33	14	1.920	1.149
The organization has talent attraction strategies which make me put more effort in my work	9	3	27	47	14	3.255	1.351
I will always better performance for the county because I have an opportunity to grow in my career	10	17	12	31	30	3.175	1.137

The findings in Table 4.1 indicated the composite average as (M=3.049), this meant that respondents moderately rated most of the statements provided under employee performance at the TransNzoia county government. In other words, there were underlying concerns about employee performance of the county government. The only issue that 76% of the respondents agreed on (M=3.847) existence talent development had increased the work output and overall county productivity which made employees work better. This findings were consistent with Achmada, Soetjipto, and Sopiah. (2022). who shared that organizations with talent development strategies make employees more productive.

On whether talent development had increased the work output and overall organization productivity, 50% of the respondents strongly agreed, 26% agreed, 11% were undecided, 9% disagreed and 4% strongly disagreed that talent development had not increased the work output and overall organization productivity, with a mean of 3.847 and standard deviation of 1.261. The findings had 76% of the respondents, being an overwhelming majority, returning a positive feedback in agreement with the statement posed to them as to whether talent development had increased the work output and overall organization productivity. This verdict was supported by the strongest mean of 3.847 compared to the other statements on this variable.

As to whether since the introduction of talent development the employees productivity had really improved in the county, 9% strongly disagreed, 17% disagreed, 27% were undecided, 33% of the respondents agreed, 14% strongly agreed that indeed since the introduction of talent development the employees productivity had really improved in the county with a mean of 1.920 and standard deviation of 1.149. From the findings, only 47% of the respondents felt that introduction of talent development programs had significantly improved employee productivity in the county while 27% of the respondents remained undecided, this was believed to be a huge number of respondents who could not either openly speak their mind or were truly not aware. However, with the majority (53%) of the respondents sounding not in approval, there was need for an audit of the efficiency of the talent development programs in the county government as regards employee performance.

On whether the county has talent attraction strategies which make employees put more effort in their work, 9% of the respondents strongly disagreed, 3% disagreed, 27% were undecided, 47% agreed while 14% strongly agreed with a mean of 3.255 and standard deviation of 1.351. Majority of the respondents (61%) returning a positive feedback, it was concluded that the county government had talent attraction strategies which made employees put more effort in their work. However, the 27% undecided respondents, which was higher than the respondents who strongly disagreed or disagreed combined, led to a conclusion that there was need for scrutiny as to why the situation was like that.

On the statement whether employees always performance better at the county because of the opportunity for them to grow in their career, 10% strongly disagreed, 17% disagreed, 12% were undecided, 31% agreed while 30% of the respondents strongly agreed that truly, employees always performance better at the county because of the opportunity for them to grow in their career with a mean value of 3.175 and standard deviation of 1.137.

4.1.1 Talent Attraction and Employee Performance

The findings on the effect of talent attraction and employee performance in TransNzoia county government, Kenya were as presented in the table below;

Table 4.2: Talent Attraction and Employee Performance

Statements	SD %	D %	UD %	A %	SA %	Mean	STDEV
The county selection and recruitment process is free and fair	19	33	32	9	7	2.642	1.361
Promotions are conducted in a free and fair manner	30	24	21	11	14	3.971	1.239
The county has good organizational climate that attract the right talent	18	15	20	30	17	4.241	1.260
The recruitment process is scientific	29	34	21	9	7	2.971	1.234

The findings in Table 4.2 indicated the value of average as $M=3.766$, this meant that respondents disagreed that there was talent attraction in TransNzoia county government, Kenya. The findings are supported by Achmada, Soetjipto and Sopiah. (2022) who observed that lack of talent attraction affects employee performance in organizations.

It was established that 7% of the respondents strongly agreed that the county selection and recruitment process is free and fair, 9% agreed, 32% were undecided, 33% disagreed and 19% strongly disagreed. It then follows that in general, 84% of the respondents had negative feedback with a mean of 2.642 that the county selection and recruitment process is not free and fair. The finding is supported by Armstrong (2020) who concluded that majority of public employment is heavily based on nepotism and tribalism.

The results showed that 14% of the respondents strongly agreed that promotions are conducted in a free and fair manner, 11% agreed, 21% were undecided, 24% disagreed and 30% strongly disagreed. Thus, 75% of the respondents generally disapproved the statement (with a Mean= 3.971) that promotions are not conducted in a free and fair manner. The finding was echoed by Dessler (2022) who said that most county promotions are not conducted in a free and fair manner.

The findings as to whether the county had good organizational climate that attract the right talent revealed that 17% strongly agreed, 30% of the respondents agreed that the county had good organizational climate that attract the right talent, 20% were undecided, 15% disagreed and 18% strongly disagreed. This meant that on overall, as to whether the county had good organizational climate that attract the right talent, 47% accepted with a mean of 4.241 and a standard deviation of 1.260. However, with a substantial percentage (20%) of respondents who remained undecided thereby leaving many unanswered questions.

The study established that only 7% of the respondents strongly agreed that the recruitment process is scientific, 9% agreed, 21% were undecided, 34% disagreed and 29% strongly disagreed. This meant that in general, 84% of the respondents who didn't support the statement (with a Mean=2.971 and a standard deviation of 1.234) that the recruitment process is scientific. The findings were consistent with Blackman and Kennedy (2023) who showed that the recruitment processes in public institutions are never scientific.

4.2. Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis was used to measure the degree of association between talent management strategies (talent attraction) and employee performance in TransNzoia County. The correlation coefficients for the variables were presented in table 4.3 below;

Table 4.3: Pearsons' Correlation Matrix

		Employee Performance	Talent Attraction
Employee Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	127	
Talent Attraction	Pearson Correlation	.729*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.223	
	N	127	127

The correlation results indicated that talent attraction had a strong, positive and statistically significant association on employee performance ($r=.729$, $p=.223$).

4.3. Regression Analysis

The study adopted a multiple linear regression model prototype to assess the combined influence of talent management strategies on employee performance in TransNzoia County.

4.3.1 Model Summary

The study model summary was presented in the table below;

Table 4.4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.798 ^a	.637	.632	1.361451

According to an accustomed R square of .637, the independent variables of the study (talent attraction) accounted for 63.7% of the changes in employee performance while the test prototype was unable to explain 36.3% of the variations in employee performance which was concluded to have been influenced by other factors beyond this study. These findings were consistent with Lydia and Kiiru (2022) who believed that one of the ways for businesses improve employee performance to outperform the competition and is to resource talent.

4.3.2 Model Suitability

The ANOVA test was used in measuring the suitability of the model in analyzing the relationship between the variables as shown in the table below:

Table 4.5: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	f	Sig.
1	Regression	30.235	1	30.235	11.899	.000 ^b
	Residual	320.121	126	2.541		
	Total	350.356	127			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant); Talent attraction, training & development, career management and talent retention

The significance value of .0000 which was less than 0.05 led to the overall model being adjudged fit for the analysis and eventual prediction of the results together with the fitting of the study multiple regression model. It was therefore adopted in determining the relationship between the independent variables (Talent attraction) and the dependent variable (Employee Performance). This was also due to the F critical at 5% level of significance was less than the F calculated value ($F_{\text{calculated}} = 11.899$), which showed that the overall model was significant.

4.3.3 Multiple Regression Analysis

The main objective of the study analyzed the influence of talent management strategies and employee performance in TransNzoia County government, Kenya. The results were as presented in table below:

Table 4.6: Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	2.624	.127		4.910	.000
	Talent Attraction	.564	.121	.434	3.156	.003

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

The established model for the study was:

$$Y = 2.624 + .564X_1$$

The multiple linear regression model extracted from the analyzed data showed that by incorporating all factors into account (talent attraction), the model holds. While by holding other variables constant at zero, employee performance was 2.624. The findings presented also show that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit increase in talent attraction would lead to a 56.4% increase in the scores of employee performance in TransNzoia County government. The findings were supported by Lydia and Kiiru (2022) who said that talent management is an important component of refining employee performance in an organization.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study findings on the talent attraction variable were that: majority of the respondents disagreed that there was talent attraction in TransNzoia county government, Kenya, as supported by Achmada, Soetjipto and Sopiah. (2022) who observed that lack of talent attraction affect employee performance in organizations. Overall, as to whether the county had good organizational climate that attract the right talent, approximately half of the respondents accepted, however, a substantial percentage of respondents remained undecided thereby leaving many unanswered questions. Majority of the respondents didn't support the statement that the recruitment process is scientific in TransNzoia County government. The findings were consistent with Blackman and Kennedy (2023) who showed that the recruitment processes in public institutions are never scientific. The following conclusions were made from the study findings: That there was little effort in TransNzoia county government towards talent attraction. This was revealed by the strength of the correlation, though positive and strong, lay at position three among the four study variables. That the county selection and recruitment process was not free and fair but heavily based on nepotism and tribalism and that promotions were not conducted in a free and fair manner. All these reasons led to the final conclusion that county lacked good organizational climate that attract the right talent since the recruitment process in the county was not scientific. From the findings of the study, the following recommendations were drawn: that TransNzoia County govern ensure that talent attraction efforts are improved for positive employee performance together with ensuring that the county selection and recruitment process is free and fair for better attraction of great talents to the work force free from tribalism and nepotism. The county to ensure that ensures are put in place to good organizational climate that attract the right talent where recruitment process is scientific.

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